

FINAL REPORT

1 General Information

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2 Summary

2.1 Summary (English)

While sensory perception and cognitive processing represent constant research topics in Neuroscience, they have seldom been investigated synergistically. Although cognitive performance is maximized only through permanent interactions with the environment, contributions of sensory stimuli to cognitive processing have largely been neglected. This is particularly evident when considering the ontogeny and maturation of limbic circuits that account for memory and executive abilities. For decades, considerable efforts have shed light on the maturation principles of sensory systems by highlighting the relevance of molecular cues, spontaneous electrical activity, and experience. More recently, some complex interactions governing the wiring of memory-relevant circuitry during development have also been resolved. The mostly separate investigation of sensory and cognitive ontogeny results from the observation that most sensory systems are underdeveloped during early life. Rodents are blind and deaf, do not whisker, and have limited motor abilities during the first days of life, and therefore, the contribution of sensory inputs to limbic ontogeny has been deemed negligible. As a notable exception, the olfactory system reaches full maturity during intrauterine life, controlling mother-offspring interactions and survival, and might shape the limbic development. Whether early olfactory inputs truly drive the development of limbic networks has, however, been unknown. The goal of our joint research project has thus been to understand structural and functional principles underlying the connectivity and communication within the main and accessory olfactory bulb (MOB and AOB, respectively) and, notably, between the OB and olfactory cortex, specifically the lateral entorhinal cortex (LEC), the gatekeeper of limbic circuitry centered on hippocampus and prefrontal cortex during neonatal and juvenile development. To test our hypotheses, we investigate wiring and firing principles within the MOB and AOB, the first processing stages of olfactory inputs, as well as between the OB and LEC. Our research reveals several key features of M/AOB physiology and, notably, OB-to-LEC communication in mice during the first and second postnatal weeks. Specifically, we have shown that spontaneously generated patterns of OB electrical activity stimulate entorhinal circuits via mono- and polysynaptic axonal projections. OB-to-LEC activity is boosted by olfactory stimuli and disrupted by chronic olfactory lesions. Therefore, spontaneous and stimulus-evoked OB activity controls neuronal network maturation in LEC.

2.2 Zusammenfassung (Deutsch)

Während Sinneswahrnehmungen und deren kognitive Verarbeitung ständige Forschungsthemen in den Neurowissenschaften sind, wurden sie bisher nur selten synergetisch unter-

sucht. Obwohl die kognitive Leistung nur durch ständige Interaktionen mit der Umwelt maximiert werden kann, wurde der Beitrag sensorischer Reize zur kognitiven Verarbeitung bisher weitgehend vernachlässigt. Dies wird besonders deutlich, wenn man die Ontogenese und Reifung limbischer Schaltkreise betrachtet, die für Gedächtnis und exekutive Fähigkeiten verantwortlich sind. Jahrzehntlang wurden erhebliche Anstrengungen unternommen, um die Prinzipien der Maturierung sensorischer Systeme zu verstehen, indem die Bedeutung molekularer Signale, spontaner elektrischer Aktivität sowie Erfahrung priorisiert wurde. In jüngerer Zeit wurden zudem komplexe Wechselwirkungen aufgeklärt, die die Verschaltung von gedächtnisrelevanten Schaltkreisen während der Entwicklung bestimmen. Die meist getrennte Untersuchung der sensorischen und kognitiven Ontogenese ergibt sich aus der Beobachtung, dass die meisten sensorischen Systeme in frühen Lebensstadien deutlich unterentwickelt sind. Neonatale Nagetiere beispielsweise sind blind und taub, nutzen keine Schnurhaare für die Wahrnehmung taktiler Reize und verfügen in den ersten Lebenstagen nur über begrenzte motorische Fähigkeiten. Daher wurde der Beitrag sensorischer Eingänge zur limbischen Ontogenese als vernachlässigbar angesehen. Eine bemerkenswerte Ausnahme bildet das Geruchssystem, das während des intrauterinen Lebens seine volle Reife erlangt und die Interaktionen zwischen Mutter und Nachwuchs steuert und möglicherweise die limbische Entwicklung beeinflusst. Ob frühe olfaktorische Stimulation tatsächlich die Entwicklung limbischer Netzwerke steuert, war bisher jedoch nicht bekannt. Ziel unseres gemeinsamen Forschungsprojekts war es daher, die strukturellen und funktionellen Prinzipien zu verstehen, die der Konnektivität und Kommunikation innerhalb des Haupt- und des akzessorischen Riechkolbens (MOB bzw. AOB) und insbesondere zwischen dem olfaktorischen Bulbus (OB) und dem olfaktorischen Kortex zugrunde liegen, insbesondere dem lateralen entorhinalen Kortex (LEC), dem Tor zu limbischen Schaltkreisen, die sich während der neonatalen und juvenilen Entwicklung auf den Hippocampus und den präfrontalen Kortex konzentrieren. Um unsere Hypothesen zu überprüfen, untersuchen wir die Verdrahtung und die Feuerprinzipien innerhalb des MOB und des AOB, den ersten Verarbeitungsstufen von olfaktorischen Eingaben, sowie zwischen OB und LEC. Unsere Forschungsergebnisse zeigen mehrere Schlüsselmerkmale der M/AOB-Physiologie und insbesondere die Existenz substantieller OB-zu-LEC-Kommunikation bei Mäusen während der ersten und zweiten postnatalen Woche. Spezifisch konnten wir zeigen, dass spontan erzeugte Muster elektrischer OB-Aktivität die entorhinalen Schaltkreise über mono- und polysynaptische axonale Projektionen stimulieren. Die OB-to-LEC-Aktivität wird durch olfaktorische Reize verstärkt und durch chronische olfaktorische Läsionen gestört. Unsere Ergebnisse demonstrieren, dass sowohl spontane, als auch durch Reize hervorgerufene OB-Aktivität die Reifung des neuronalen Netzwerks im LEC steuert.

3 Progress Report

The intricate interactions between the prefrontal cortex (PFC), hippocampus (HP), and entorhinal cortex (EC) in mnemonic and executive tasks emphasize their role as core components of cognition-relevant limbic circuitry. The mutual information exchange between these areas occurs through direct axonal pathways or specific relay stations, controlled by feedback interactions facilitated by network oscillations. These oscillations provide precise temporal windows for neural activity, allowing one brain area to read the content encoded by another. A wealth of studies has shown that changes in coordinated activity patterns are associated with large-scale neural network functions involved in various cognitive (Buzsáki, 2006; Buzsáki and Vöröslakos, 2023). Even long before cognitive maturation, oscillatory activity is present and controls the local and large-scale brain wiring along development. For instance, simultaneous recordings from PFC and HP have demonstrated that, early in life, hippocampal theta-band activity modulates the firing of prefrontal neurons via monosynaptic glutamatergic inputs from CA1 and subiculum (Ahlbeck et al., 2018). This temporal coordination is critical for the maturation of working-memory performance. The EC is also involved in memory processing, acting as a gatekeeper for limbic networks throughout lifespan (Fernández and Tendolkar, 2006). Its connectivity facilitates the entrainment of prefrontal-hippocampal-entorhinal networks in oscillatory rhythms during encoding and retrieval of declarative memory.

The EC also relays sensory information to limbic networks. Especially, the lateral EC (LEC) receives direct input from the OB (Sosulski et al., 2011) and further projects to HP and PFC (Hartung et al., 2016). This pathway might modulate olfactory coding by providing contextual modulation of cortical odor processing. However, little is known about LEC sensory physiology and its functional role in odor-specific activity remains elusive. The olfactory system's wiring scheme is conserved across species (Touhara and Vosshall, 2009). In rodents, mitral cell axons terminate on apical dendrites of layer II/III pyramidal and stellate cells in the LEC, which project back to PC and OB. Mitral/tufted cells represent OB's sole output neurons but are part of a complex network that controls odor information coding through inhibitory interneurons like periglomerular and granule cells (Wachowiak and Shipley, 2006).

Despite its importance in newborns and juveniles, the functional development of OB beyond anatomical aspects, and its role for the wiring of entorhinal-prefrontal-hippocampal circuits are still unresolved. Therefore, whether olfaction controls the maturation of neuronal networks underlying cognitive processing remains an open question. Notably, rodent pups rely heavily on olfaction during early life due to underdeveloped other sensory systems (Logan et

al., 2012). Their sense of smell is particularly relevant for pup survival, and the olfactory system is considered more mature at birth than other sensory systems. Unlike most sensory pathways, the olfactory system bypasses a thalamic relay and directly conveys information from OB to cortical areas. During development, sensory inputs have been shown to induce coordinated activity patterns in cortical circuits (Hanganu-Opatz, 2010). Even earlier in life, discontinuous oscillations entrain the developing circuits and are generated endogenously at the sensory periphery (e.g. retinal waves, passive activation of whiskers). Are these endogenous- and stimulus-induced patterns of activity present in the developing OB too? Do they contribute to the development of OB circuitry and the wiring of downstream LEC-HP-PFC?

The project we report on has addressed these questions, successfully combining the expertise from the IHO (ontogeny of cognitive processing) and MS (olfactory system physiology) labs. The main aim was to uncover how olfactory processing early in life influences neural communication within developing prefrontal-hippocampal-entorhinal networks. Our studies provided a mechanistic understanding of OB input-output relationships, detailed anatomical mapping of OB-LEC connectivity, and in-depth dissection of OB-LEC-HP-PFC wiring along development. The project's specific aims included understanding structural principles governing OB-LEC connectivity during development *versus* adulthood; identifying electrophysiological signatures of OB-to-LEC communication; elucidation of olfactory impact on limbic circuit development; and understanding how manipulation during defined developmental periods affects entorhinal-prefrontal-hippocampal circuitry and cognitive abilities.

Ultimately, our collaborative research seeks to provide insights into how sensory stimulation impacts central circuit consolidation and cognitive behavior by integrating complementary anatomical and physiological approaches within a conceptual framework linking sensory input with cognitive neurobiology development.

In the following, we will briefly introduce four collaborative studies that resulted from the project and highlight their major knowledge gain. For a full list of publications see **4**.

Our central study (Gretenkord et al., 2019) investigated the patterns of coordinated electrical activity in the OB and their influence on the oscillatory entrainment of the LEC during early development. Combining anatomical tracing with in vivo electrophysiology, optogenetics, pharmacology and sensory manipulations, we demonstrated that (i) two major patterns of coordinated activity entrain the neonatal OB: continuous slow frequency oscillations temporally related to respiration and discontinuous theta band oscillations critically depending on MTC activity, (ii) both rhythms temporally couple the neonatal OB and LEC, with OB theta bursts boosting the oscillatory entrainment and firing within entorhinal circuits via mono- and

polysynaptic projections, (iii) olfactory stimuli augment oscillatory power, induce activity in fast frequency bands, and strengthen the coupling within OB-LEC circuits, and (iv) olfactory activation during the first postnatal week is critical for the functional development of entorhinal circuits. These data reveal that endogenously-generated and stimulus-driven activities in OB control the oscillatory entrainment of LEC during early development. The results of this first study led us propose that endogenously generated and odor-evoked OB activity, especially as a result of maternal odor, might increase the level of excitability within entorhinal-prelimbic-hippocampal networks and strengthen their wiring. By these means, the olfactory system could facilitate the postnatal maturation of limbic circuitry and, ultimately, the emergence of cognitive abilities. Besides this knowledge gain, the study provided substantial methodological development. Novel paradigms for multi-site and -area recordings and optogenetic manipulations in the brain of pups in vivo have been established.

In a second study (Kostka et al., 2020), we proceeded addressing the role of MTCs in the early postnatal development of limbic circuits, focusing on how the MC firing entrain the entorhinal circuits. Combining in vivo and in vitro patch-clamp recordings from MCs with extracellular recordings of LFP and spiking activity in OB and LEC, we demonstrated that (i) during early postnatal development (P8 – 10) MCs display either irregular bursting or non-bursting firing characteristics, (ii) irregular bursting MCs display less pronounced hyperpolarization-evoked sag currents when compared to non-bursting MCs, (iii) the firing of bursting MCs concentrate during theta events and is more precisely locked to the phase of theta oscillations in the neonatal OB, and (iv) bursting MCs temporally relate to oscillatory patterns in neonatal LEC. These findings suggest that predominantly bursting MTCs synchronize neuronal ensembles in discontinuous theta oscillations in the developing OB and LEC.

Our second study provides new insights into the cellular substrate of OB-LEC interaction, demonstrating that bursting MCs play a prominent role in shaping neonatal theta rhythm and facilitating the oscillatory entrainment of developing limbic circuits. Bursting MCs are proposed to transmit information more reliably, activate entorhinal networks, and strengthen connectivity between OB and LEC during neonatal development. Olfactory drive is suggested to augment entorhinal circuit excitability, promoting organization into oscillatory ensembles, which are relayed to the hippocampus. Overall, this study sheds light on the functional properties of MCs during early postnatal development and their crucial role in shaping neural circuits involved in cognitive performance.

In a third related study (Tsitoura et al., 2020), we benefitted from our joint expertise in analyzing oscillatory network mechanisms. Our previous research had shed light on the infra-slow

oscillatory discharge of projection neurons in the mouse AOB, revealing synchronized microcircuits that subdivide the brain region into segregated functional clusters (Gorin et al., 2016). Using miniature microscopes to image calcium dynamics *in vivo*, we now demonstrated that infra-slow periodic patterns of neural activity reflect the default AOB output state in awake male and female mice. This rhythmic activity is driven by intrinsically rhythmogenic pacemaker-like neurons entraining members of the same local network motif via excitatory synaptic input. The findings also suggest potential implications for sensory information processing, including increased coding capacity and enhanced connectivity within the accessory olfactory bulb as well as dynamic gating, reliability, and selectivity of communication with downstream networks. In summary, this research provides valuable insights into the functional organization and physiological principles underlying the role of the accessory olfactory system in social information processing.

Finally, the fourth study (Song et al., 2022) was inspired by our joint efforts to disentangle the interactions and oscillatory coupling between PFC, HP, and LEC. Many decades ago, disturbed interactions between HP and PFC has been proposed as a core aspect of pathophysiology in psychiatric disorders. Especially in schizophrenia, the prefrontal-hippocampal impairment might link the neurodevelopmental dysfunction and later behavioral deficits. In this study, we investigated a mouse model of disease that mimics the dual genetic-environmental etiology of disease (GE mice) and monitored the structure and function of prefrontal-hippocampal connectivity along the entire development. For this, we combined *in vivo* electrophysiology and optogenetics with tracing of projections. We showed that in GE mice (i) the sparser axonal projections from HP to PL act as substrate of diminished HP-PFC communication throughout postnatal development; (ii) presynaptic abnormality of hippocampal terminals and their poorer efficiency in activating the PL cause miswiring of long-range connectivity, and (iii) the deficits of hippocampal projections persist, yet at a lower magnitude, until pre-juvenile age. This sparser and less efficient connectivity as well as cellular dysfunction are the substrate of the weaker excitatory drive from hippocampus to prefrontal cortex as well as of poorer oscillatory coupling between the two brain areas in these mice. We demonstrated that, while the structural and functional connectivity deficits persist during the entire development, their magnitude decreases with age. The results added experimental evidence for the developmental miswiring hypothesis of psychiatric disorders. Moreover, the study enabled to develop novel protocols for in-depth dissection of connectivity in the immature brain.

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4 Published Project Results

4.1 Publications with scientific quality assurance

1. Gorin, M., Tsitoura, C., Kahan, A., Watznauer, K., Drose, D. R., Arts, M., Mathar, R., O'Connor, S., **Hanganu-Opatz, I. L.**, Ben-Shaul, Y., & **Spehr, M.** (2016). Interdependent Conductances Drive Intraslow Intrinsic Rhythmogenesis in a Subset of Accessory Olfactory Bulb Projection Neurons. *The Journal of Neuroscience*, *36*(11), 3127–3144. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.2520-15.2016>
2. Gretenkord, S., Kostka, J. K., Hartung, H., Watznauer, K., Fleck, D., Minier-Toribio, A., **Spehr, M.**, & **Hanganu-Opatz, I. L.** (2019). Coordinated electrical activity in the olfactory bulb gates the oscillatory entrainment of entorhinal networks in neonatal mice. *PLOS Biology*, *17*(1), e2006994. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2512328>
3. Tsitoura, C., Malinowski, S. T., Mohrhardt, J., Degen, R., DiBenedictis, B. T., Gao, Y., Watznauer, K., Gerhold, K., Nagel, M., Weber, M., Rothermel, M., **Hanganu-Opatz, I. L.**, Ben-Shaul, Y., Davison, I. G., & **Spehr, M.** (2020). Synchronous Infra-Slow Oscillations Organize Ensembles of Accessory Olfactory Bulb Projection Neurons into Distinct Microcircuits. *The Journal of Neuroscience*, *40*(21), 4203–4218. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.2925-19.2020>
4. Kostka, J. K., Gretenkord, S., **Spehr, M.**, & **Hanganu-Opatz, I. L.** (2020). Bursting mitral cells time the oscillatory coupling between olfactory bulb and entorhinal networks in neonatal mice. *Journal of Physiology*, *598*(24), 5753–5769. <https://doi.org/10.1113/JP280131>
5. Bitzenhofer, S.H., Pöplau, J.A., **Hanganu-Opatz, I.L.** (2020) Gamma activity accelerates during prefrontal development. *Elife*, *18*:9:e56795. <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.56795>.

6. Song, L., Xu, X., Putthoff, P., Fleck, D., **Spehr, M.**, & **Hanganu-Opatz, I. L.** (2022). Sparser and Less Efficient Hippocampal-Prefrontal Projections account for Developmental Network Dysfunction in a Model of Psychiatric Risk Mediated by Gene-Environment Interaction. *The Journal of Neuroscience*, 42(4), 601–618. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.1203-21.2021>
7. Wiegert*, J. S., **Spehr***, **M.**, & **Hanganu-Opatz***, **I. L.** (2023). Systems neuroscience: A box full of tools to illuminate the black box of the brain. *PLOS Biology*, 21(7), e3002221. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3002221>

4.2 Other publications and published results

8. **Spehr, M.**, & **Hanganu-Opatz, I. L.** (2022). Editorial. *Neuroforum*, 28(3), 127–128. <https://doi.org/10.1515/nf-2022-0013>

4.3 Patents (applied for and granted)

N/A